

ABU ABDULLAH MUHAMMAD IBN ALI HAKIM TERMIZI EDUCATION OF THE SOUL IN THE WRITING AND THE FOOLED PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS

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Abstract. When the nafs brings falsehood, oppression, and lies, it blinds its owner, adorns him, deceives him, distracts him, and this deception continues. Airy desires are the chess of the nafs. He occupies the cells of truth one by one, and finally frees the soul from the truth. He who is deceived is deceived by his own inexperience and ignorance. He obeys the commands of the nafs with his heart. Hawaiian desires in the shadow of lust will gradually pass their judgment on lust.

Keywords: lust, lie, deception, heart, desire, ignorance, lust, truth, justice, correctness.

Praise be to Allah, the One who is worthy of praise. Messenger, prophet and blessings be upon his servant. We have seen that the religion of Allah has three pillars: truth, justice, built on righteousness. Righteousness is entrusted to the members, justice to the hearts, and righteousness to the minds. Tomorrow, when we approach the scale to weigh the deeds, the good deeds will be right, evils are placed on the circle of justice, on the tongue of the scales of righteousness. With that Good things like the end of God's pleasure from his servants to his servants the severity of the evils will be known. Anyone who is a combination of these three things: if the truth disappears from it, falsehood will replace it. If justice is lost from him, instead oppression will come. If truth is lost from it, falsehood will replace it. These are the three things is the army of enlightenment. The three things that are against them are the air of lust is an army. Nafs is a container of air. He surrounds the deceived.

If you pay attention, al-Hakim at-Tirmizi light, knowledge, heart and in general, purity, He puts concepts such as fear of God on the same line. of these concepts all of them are combined together, and as a result, the sharp differences between them are even becoming less noticeable. So, in Sufi teachings, light and knowledge are the same thing viewed, they are interpreted together as the basis of mysteries. Light - inspiration, emotion, a symbol of excitement and the beginning of enlightenment, science - a prelude to

systematization, an integral part of the theoretical field and the Muslim world, Sufi enlightenment According to Professor J. Omonturdiyev, people spend a lot of time They used "Navroznama" and "Solnoma" as folnoma and tolenoma, its essence - its logical basis is not related to some real reality those who could not distinguish from the sides. Hakim Termizi himself has every statement at the end, saying "wallahu a'lam bissawab" ("Allah alone knows the truth"). wrote This is humility. In "Navroznama" and "Solnoma" earth life is planets studied in connection with the movement. In other words, earth life, people destiny and others depending on which day of the week Navrozi Olam enters defined. At first glance, this seems like an absurd statement. But the scientist of the week states that the year in which "such and such" day falls belongs to "such and such" planet, from an astrologer's point of view, there is serious wisdom behind it is felt. Because the earth, including man, seven different planets (the Sun, (Moon, Mirrih, Atorud, Mushtari, Zuhra, Zuhul), so seven years he lives under the influence of different realities, surrounded by different environments. Hakim Termizi is influenced by this environment, including the destiny of man and his client calendared the changes that would occur In Sufism, knowledge is given by the term "light", that is, light-science, knowledge and in turn it is light. According to the Qur'an, light is only from Allah will be awarded. Nur-Sadiq leads his servant to true faith, that is, faith in the heart If light is a form of knowledge (knowledge of God), then faith is the light itself. In the Qur'an It is said that "Allah leads to His light every servant He wants." These are Mansur In the cities of Halloj (857-922) it sounds like this: "He who enlightens hearts thing is God's light, God sends light to people. The light of inspiration is in the human head, the light of conversation is between the two eyebrows (forehead), the light of nearness (confidence) is in the ear, clarity the light is in the tongue, the light of faith is in the chest"

CONCLUSION

The believers were freed from this attachment by the blessing of monotheism that God gave them. They worshiped only Allah. They believed that all benefits and harms are from Him alone. They only hoped for him. They prayed to him alone. Then there are pros and cons they were deceived by reasons. This is the work of the ego. And the heart, in every work, is a sign to God does. Considers it. Nafs, things, the reasons hidden in them reflects. His secret - "He gave it to you from the hands of men, from heaven, from the earth, the sun, the moon, heat, cold, and behavior. He is the original giver. The wounded blocked Him from you. You will receive from them in front of your eyes. This is in his heart he demanded that you get these things from Allah

Almighty. It's in your head let your eyes see all things and communicate this to your inner eye gave for The light of life of the soul is due to this eye. Life is always in the eyes of the heart -The Eternal One has light. Always life - inwardly with the light of life of the Eternal One things, i.e. rububiyat, are perceived. When the light of the mind's eye increases, so does your seeing and knowing. If if there is an obstacle such as a cloud blocking the vision, the weakness of the vision and the middle due to the blocking cloud, things appear blurred and you cannot see. Same so, if the eyes of the soul are prevented from seeing by a cloud of sins and vices, ignorance If the air is blocked by the smoke and the dust of the soul, understand the works of Allah Almighty you cannot, because of the weakness of your heart, you cannot see these things. That's why you are lust you believe the scams you called.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. А.Б.Қодирова. PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF SELF-EDUCATION IN THE WORK OF ABU ABDULLAH MUHAMMAD IBN ALI HAKIM TERMEZI "THE WISE AND THE DECEIVED" Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems 12 (6), 1143-1146, 2020.119-123p.
2. Qodirova A. B. AN ANALYSIS OF THE SCIENTIFIC CONTENT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL VIEWS AND THEORY OF SUFISM IN THE WORKS OF AL-KHAKIM ATTERMIZI. TOSHKENT DAVLAT PEDAGOGIKA UNIVERSITETI ILMIY AXBOROTLARI 2021/1-SON.137-p
3. Termizi, Abu Abdullah Muhammad ibn Ali Hakim. Wise men an the deceived/Abu Abdullah Muhammad ibn Ali Hakim Termiz; translator: A. Rahmatullaev; Imam Termizi international scientific researh center.- Tashkent: Movarounnahr, 2018-96 p.